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Industry Advisory Board Members' Contributions to Engineering Education Program Development A Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Engineering education programs should be developed in line with society's needs. This becomes more challenging with an increased speed of technical development. In order to create this alignment input from society and industry is vital for program management as well as for higher education governance. One common way to gather input is through industry advisory boards on different organisational levels. Currently there are few studies that focus on contributions by industry representatives in industry advisory boards on individual education program level. These studies have primarily been performed through quantitative approaches (surveys) and findings are inconclusive.

In this original study we aim to answer how industry representatives contribute to program development of engineering education programs, and what their motives are. In order to gain increased understanding, we have performed 18 semi-structured interviews with industry representatives in program advisory boards at one Swedish university.

Results indicate that industry representatives provide different types of contributions, which are affected by preconditions set by heads of programme, and meeting formats. Several representatives mention that they are unclear of their actual contribution. They also highlight (1) personal motives such as supporting the head of programme and (2) their employers' motives to actively influence program content, as motives for contributions.

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This study adds new insights, through its qualitative approach, to the understanding of industry representatives' motives and contributions to program development. It provides additional perspectives to current contributions to this field, to program management, and for development of governance structures in higher education institutions.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In higher education in general, and for engineering programmes specifically, it is important that the content of education meets the current and future needs of the industry, and that the study programme is attractive to potential and current students. In developing programmes and courses, it is important from a strategic as well as from an operational perspective that teachers and programme gain understanding of the needs of the labour market.

Industry needs can be captured through contacts between universities and representatives from the industry. One way of doing so is to involve industry representatives in various forums and decision-making bodies linked to study programmes. In program advisory boards, industry representatives from program-relevant companies and organisations can share experience and industry perspectives with other members of the board; students, teachers and program management. At Chalmers University of Technology, a project has been under way since 2017 aimed at creating effective program advisory boards.

The number of previous studies of industry representatives in the development of educational programs in higher education are few. Genheimer and Shahab (2007, 2009) have published results from survey-based studies where school directors and advisory board members of 90 American engineering programmes were asked about the advisory boards work and efficiency. The advisory boards in the studies (Genheimer and Shahab, 2007; 2009) were all in higher education institutions or on department level and the studies had focus on financing of schools and programs. Viswanathan (2012) performed an interdisciplinary study at the National University of Singapore, where he argues for the importance of advisory boards for program development. Emmer and Ghanem (2013) present the results of an American survey-based study where programme managers and program advisory board members answered questions about the program advisory boards impact on the development of construction management program curriculum. El Refae, Askari and Alnaji (2016) question whether program advisory boards affect quality of education and report the results of a small survey at a university in the United Arab Emirates. All of these studies are based on questionnaires with a quantitative research approach.

In this study, we explore the field of program advisory boards (PAB) for individual engineering study programs (BEng and MEng) through interviews with industry representatives (IR) that are members of program advisory boards at Chalmers University of Technology in Sweden, in order to better understand their contributions to programme development, as well as their motives.

1.2 Aim

This study aims to address the issues: How do industry representatives in programme advisory boards contribute to programme development, and what are their motives?

2 RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODS

In order to gain increased understanding of how industry representatives contribute to programme development and what their motives are, we have performed an original study applying a qualitative research design.

The main method used is interviews with industry representatives in advisory boards for individual engineering programmes.

Programmes studied are sampled from all four educational areas at Chalmers University of Technology in Gothenburg, Sweden. The areas are: Architecture and Urban Design (ASAM), Mechanical engineering, Mechatronics and Automation, Design as well as Shipping and Marine Engineering (MATS), Electrical Engineering, Computer Technology, IT and Industrial Engineering and Management (EDIT-I), and Physics, Chemistry and Bioengineering, as well as Mathematics and Engineering Preparatory Year (KFM).

Interview respondents were identified and selected through sampling (Descombe, 2010). Sample criteria used were Master of Science in Engineering (8 respondents)/ Bachelor of Science in Engineering programmes (8 and 10 respondents), male/female board member (12 and 6 respondents), and first term in advisory board / more than one term in advisory board (13 and 5 respondents). 14 respondents represent large organisations (>1000 employees), in manufacturing, telecom, construction, and consulting industries. Four respondents represent small organisations (<100 employees), mainly from technical consultancy firms, but also from one industry association. Most respondents (14) have 5-12 years relevant work experience, and four have more than 15 years experience.

In all 18 semi-structured interviews lasting 45-75 minutes each were performed. Interview questions (see Appendix A) are primarily based on a survey performed by Genheimer and Shahab (2007; 2009), and adjusted and expanded to better fit an interview format. Interviews were recorded if the respondent did not decline when asked, and were written down and summarised before the data was jointly analysed using thematic analysis (Sullivan and Forrester, 2019) by both authors. For the first part of the aim (how industry representatives contribute) the following themes were inductively identified: Time perspective (either strategic long-term, or detail-oriented, short term). Self-image (either performance management oriented, or advisory oriented / mentorship). Degree of abstraction (either concrete contributions, or more abstract reasoning). For the second part of the aim (what are the industry representatives' motives for contributing), these themes were inductively identified: Focus (for themselves, for their organisation, or for society). Contributions (to the program, or to the university). Reason (future impact, or reciprocation).

3 RESULTS

Industry representatives' (IR) contributions to the programme advisory board's (PAB) work are mainly in connection with meetings, which is why meetings, including preparation and post-work, are focused in this study.

3.1 Motives

Industry representatives express various reasons for participation in the PAB work. One reason mentioned by many is to bring “reality-perspective”, in addition to the academic perspective held by teachers and programme management, into PAB and in development of study programmes. IR point out the importance of having influence on the programmes development to ensure it is aligned with industry's needs.

Several IR who previously have been students at the university express that they are part of the PAB because it gives them a chance to pay back to the programme or the university. They say that through their participation in the PAB, they want to make imprints and benefits for programme development. Several IR also state that they have a recruitment perspective on their participation; students met in PAB can be a potential future employee, IR get an understanding of today's students' and education's content and that they have the opportunity to influence the programme development for future recruitment needs.

Most IR express the importance of having the feeling of contributing, both in the moment at the meetings but also longterm through knowledge of making a difference in program development.

Several IR see that PAB meetings are opportunities for networking and providing opportunities to meet different people (students, teachers and industry colleagues). They also express an aim to receive information that can be of use in their home-organisation.

Another motive expressed for IR to participate and contribute to PAB work is that it adds to personal development, it is interesting, fun and it caters to the personal curiosity about what is happening in the programme and at the university. Several IR adds that it feels rewarding to give back to the HEI (Higher Education Institute).

The reasons that IR express for participating in the board can be divided into two main categories: Personal interest, and as a representative of the organisation in which they are employed. The two categories coincide to some extent.

3.2 How to contribute to programme development?

There are different preconditions for IR possibilities to contribute to programme development in PAB.

Recruitment of IR is one of these preconditions. The majority of IR in PAB are recruited via the heads' of programme personal networks. IR mention that they have been approached in different ways; after coincidental meetings, via an e-mail “from their previous thesis tutor”, or as an old personal friend to the head of programme. However,

a few of the IR have been involved since their home organisation (company or industry association) have approached the university or the head of programme directly and asked to be a part of the board.

Most of the IR are alumni from the programme or the HEI. They bring previous understanding of programme designs as well as from the specific university. Some of the IR have no previous experience from the programme or the university.

Differences in meeting structure have a big impact on PAB work, according to IR. Frequency of board meetings differs, from one meeting a year to six meetings. Low frequency of meetings (one-two meetings a year) IR experience that it is hard to feel engaged in the process of programme development.

How time is distributed between heads of programme and other board members during meetings is also mentioned as a structural matter of importance. Many of the IR express that large parts of the meetings are occupied with programme information (statistics of student performance, course evaluations etcetera) presented by the head of programme. Several IR point out that time for discussion amongst amongst board members is essential. Some PAB are smaller than others and depending on the number of board members, IR claim that discussion works well when the group is small (eight people or less) but when the board has more members, IR experience it is more effective when the group is divided into smaller units. It gives everyone time to talk and share their experience. There is a consistency amongst IR, that their contribution, industry experience, is critical for programme development.

In addition to requirements of time, frequency and group size, most IR also request more material to prepare prior to meetings. That would increase the quality of discussions during meetings. IR suggest that preparations can include involvement from the company/organisation where they are employed, through getting questions or topics to discuss, in order to get more and diverse information from industry. Meeting agendas are in most cases sent out prior to PAB meetings but rarely other material for preparations.

Several IR call for more and better feedback on PAB work and their own contributions. Many IR express that they are uncertain of their impact on the programmes development and call for better feedback on that. A suggestion from one IR is that each PAB meeting connects to the previous meeting and what has happened since then. IR also point out that they feel more involved in PAB work when meeting notes are distributed after board meetings.

During interviews IR express different views of their role and on PAB aim. Some IR focus on details and operational work, others focus on longterm goals and strategic objectives.

3.3 Contributions to programme development

When asked about current contributions to program development all interviewees mention that they add worklife reality, what is needed when the students graduate and gets employed. Most IR also mention that they add business perspective to

discussions on program development, either from a current perspective (what is needed today), or from a future perspective (what will be needed in the future).

Other aspects that a few IR mention that they contribute with today, and that many IR see that they may do in the future, are by being involved in thesis work (as tutors, project initiators, or as entry points to thesis coordinators within their home organisation), by participating in courses as guest lecturers or alumni witnesses, as organisers of field trips and study visits, and by participating in different program marketing events (both directed towards potential students, as well as towards current students).

Several of the interviewees mention that in they experience that their contributions to board discussions are given high importance by the heads of programme.

4 DISCUSSION

IR are willing to contribute to programme development in different ways. However, certain criteria need to be fulfilled in order strengthen the work done by PAB. In this chapter results from interviews with IR are discussed.

4.1 Expectations, contribution and reward

Coe (2008) propose that the initial activity when designing an advisory board system is to decide and to be clear on what you (the HEI) want the board to do, and to communicate this clearly to the board members. Within the group of IR interviewed it is noticeable that they are of different opinion regarding their role in PAB; some see themselves as advisors to programme management, while others have a mindset of being part of a board of directors. This difference in mindset affects their expectation on PAB discussions – is input from the board a direct basis for decision making, or is it ideas and viewpoints to programme management to be considered, amongst other perspectives, when heads of programme make decisions?

The IR point out how important it is to be heard and to feel involved in making a difference in programme development. If feeling involved and being heard is an essential reward for contributing (in line with common motivation theories such as Hackman and Oldham, 1976) and PAB is the forum where industry experience is captured, structure of meetings etc., should support IR's request. Otherwise PAB aim will be jeopardised and study programme development will risk being onesided with only the academic perspective represented.

HEI have long decision processes, the organisations are hierarchic surrounded by a considerable amount of rules and regulations, therefore are longterm cooperation with industry representatives is vital for programme development. Some IR mention that they have been board members for a shorter period of time (less than two years) and that changes are not visible in such a short timeframe.

To avoid the risk of disjointed processes and decisions and risk of loosing engagement of IR, it is important to have balance between IR contributions and perceived rewards (in line with Hackman and Oldham, 1976). Rewards can be immediate through feedback during and between meetings, or long-term thorough implemented changes

in programme design, programme content, or course content. One of the most strongly pronounced motives for contributing is “making a difference”. Rewards through feedback and programme development is however delusive; how can a single IR see his or her contribution when decisions and changes include the work of many different people and perspectives often adjusted do fit into an existing organisation with high sets of rules, regulations and culture?

4.2 Obstacles

Most of the IRs are recruited from the heads of programme personal network. This creates a certain homogeneity among board members, as well as a certain loyalty from IRs towards the heads of programme. Previous studies (Genheimer and Shehab, 2009) have concluded that when IR are alumni, they display a strong loyalty towards the university. If ambition is to increase experience and different points of views in discussions heterogeneous group compositions are preferred.

Coe (2008) stresses the importance of having a chair with strong leadership skills in order to creating a positive experience of advisory boards. Observations in this study show that heads of programme have a decisive impact on how IR experience the role the PAB. If discussions in board meetings are aimed to have an effect on the results/education, then the character of information presented should be aligned with the type of influences/effects desired, and with the purpose of the board. For example, if information related to course evaluation is sent to IRs, and this is pointed out as a problem, then it is likely that the board will focus on supporting the head of programme to some that specific problem, instead of discussing program issues on the strategic level as originally intended. If this type of misalignment is continued, there is a risk that the PABs' purpose change permanently.

Coe (2008) also mention the importance of having as prepared a constitution including a clear statement of goals and mission. Several of the IRs mention a desire to receive material, preferably with a clear assignment or questions to reflect upon, sufficiently in advance in order to prepare themselves as well as having time to discuss within their home organisations prior to PAB meetings. They claim it will help them to feel useful and important, having well prepared thoughts and ideas into the meetings. On the other hand, during the interviews several IRs expressed that they felt unsure of how their contributions has short-term effects in terms of what is discussed, or what is decided during meetings. A study of heads of programmes and their experiences from advisory board interaction (Kullberg and Paulin, 2019a; 2019b) indicate that heads of programme are reluctant to burden IR with too much material and preparations, again pointing at the importance of managing expectations.

There were also comments made by IRs that reports regarding, for example student throughput, presented by heads of programme can be hard to relate to discussions in previous meetings. There are also expressions of frustration from not seeing how they (IRs) can affect key performance indicators, such as student throughput.

Another aspect of programme development brought up by IRs during interviews is that they have problems in seeing concrete changes in programme design, improvements in course evaluation results, or student throughput, as a result of board activities.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

The main conclusions related to how IR contribute to programme development are: IR bring the reality perspective into programme development which is important to better align education to society's needs.

IR contribute to programme development during board meetings, and the type of contributions made are influenced by signals conveyed by the heads of programme via the types of information presented during meetings.

IR contributions are affected by feedback with different time frames, immediate during meetings regarding personal contributions, short-term from one meeting to another highlighting actions taken after the previous meeting, and long-term from one academic year to another regarding programme development.

The main motives for IR to contribute are:

To pay back to the programme or university for the education and experiences that they have received.

To make an imprint on programme content and thereby knowledge of the future workforce.

5.2 Recommendations

If heads of programme, and other decision makers, want to include important industry perspectives in programme development via program advisory boards, we propose that:

IR are recruited from a broader base than in the studied case (mainly personal networks of heads of programme) in order to bring heterogeneity and thereby additional perspectives into strategic discussions.

When designing meeting formats, several aspects should be considered. Before meetings, sufficient time and material for preparations is desired by IRs. The type of information send out should be aligned with the desired purpose of the board whether that is the board as a "strategic council" or an "operational control function". Allocation of meeting time should include significant time for recurring small group discussions, and/or workshops, in order for the IRs to experience that they can contribute, time for specific follow-up from previous meetings of strategic level development primarily, and operational level development occasionally.

We also recommend that universities as well as heads of programme clarify the purpose of the PAB to each member in the board, and expectations on board members' contributions. We also want to highlight the importance to listen to the expectations of IRs and take these into consideration when possible. We stress that heads of programme inform each board member of the conditions under which the board operates as well as the conditions under which the heads of programme operate, for example in terms of decision making processes with the university. Finally, we recommend that IRs provide feedback of how they perceive decision making processes relevant for the purpose of the board.

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APPENDIX A

Interview Questions – Program Advisory Board

Aim: How do industry representatives in programme advisory boards contribute to programme development, and what are their motives?

Background information

What is your name?

What organization do you currently work for?

What is your job position?

Describe your work experience?

Are you an alumnus?

For how long have you been a member of the advisory board?

How were you recruited into the board?

Which study program, and educational area, is your advisory board connected to?

Questions

How were you approached and asked to be part of the advisory board?

Why did you want to be part of the advisory board, when asked?

Why do you want to be part of the advisory board, today?

What do you want to get out of your participation in the advisory board? What is “in it” for you?

Do you get that? Please, elaborate.

What development phase would you say that your program is in? Development, or more of a steady-state phase?

What do you normally discuss during the board meetings? What type of questions?

How do you contribute to the board? Content wise? Speaking space?

How often do you have board meetings?

Do you have other meetings within the board?

How often do you participate?

Are the head of programme, and board members in contact with each other in between board meetings?

If yes, what type of contacts (phone, e-mail, meetings)? How often? For what reasons?

Please, describe a typical board meeting.

What is the purpose and aim of the board?

How important is that purpose?

How effective would you say that your board is (with regards to fulfilling the purpose)?

What is the overall effectiveness/efficiency of your board?

How do you perceive that input provided by the board is received by the head of programme and the university?

Additional comments?